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Review Article

**ROLE OF FLUID RESUSCITATION IN THE MANAGEMENT
OF SEPSIS AND SEPTIC SHOCK**Hamad Ahmad¹, FNU Neelma¹, Salman Haider¹, Ishtiaq Ahmad¹¹Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, PakistanEmail Address: hamad.ahd691@gmail.com**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Sepsis is a systemic inflammatory response to severe infection that may cause significant morbidity and mortality and is one of the most common conditions in the patients admitted to the Intensive Care Unit. This article focuses on the role of fluid therapy and the outcomes of different approaches towards fluid administration in patients with sepsis and septic shock. In the era of modern medical science, management of sepsis has always been a major challenge and that is why the development of sepsis in critically ill patients is always considered a bad prognostic indicator. Antibiotics and fluids resuscitation are the fundamentals in the management of sepsis. The sensitivity of the bugs causing sepsis determines the choice of the antibiotics but fluid resuscitation can be challenging at times. Crystalloids are considered the fluids of the first choice in patients with sepsis. Different compositions of the intravenous fluids have different effects on the organs, hence care must be taken while choosing a specific type of fluid for treating a patient with sepsis. The risk of kidney injury and death appears to be greater with semi-synthetic colloids than with crystalloids. The quantity of fluid administered places a pivotal role in the outcome of patients with sepsis. We have found in our review that excess fluid administration can be harmful at times and may even worsen the shock while a more restrictive and individualized approach to fluid resuscitation may demonstrate improved outcomes. Hence, we suggest that the type of fluid administered and the quantity should be tailored through an individualized and physiologic approach to decrease the morbidity and mortality associated with sepsis.

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INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND:

Sepsis is defined as a systemic inflammatory syndrome in the presence of widespread infection. The basic pathophysiology behind the septic shock is the inability of the circulatory system to provide sufficient blood, oxygen, and nutrients and to remove the metabolic wastes from the peripheral tissues due to excessive vasodilation induced by widespread infection in a critically ill patient [1]. Decreased vasomotor tone and capillary endothelial dysfunction associated with sepsis results in the loss of intravascular fluids into extravascular compartments, causing hypotension and circulatory collapse. Fluid resuscitation has been the mainstay in the management of septic shock. Administration of intravenous fluids replenishes the intravascular fluids lost and increases the fluid volume leading to increased tissue perfusion and oxygen delivery by increasing preload, stroke volume, and ultimately the cardiac output [2]. The spectrum of severity ranges from sepsis to septic shock with an estimated mortality of 10% to greater than 40% when signs of shock manifest. Management also varies for the different spectrum of severity i.e life-saving measures for those with septic shock may lead to overtreatment to those with mild variant sepsis and vice versa [3]. Overtreatment or undertreatment with fluid administration has shown to have a poor outcome and may result in increased mortality. Hence, proper care should be taken in fluid resuscitation while managing patients with sepsis and septic shock.

REVIEW:

Literature was searched in PubMed using different keywords for data collection. Online resources regarding the current protocol in sepsis management were also searched. The keywords used were: fluid resuscitation in sepsis, pathophysiology of septic shock, and liberal vs restricted approach to fluid resuscitation in sepsis and septic shock.

The following inclusion criteria were used for study selection: human subjects only, papers published in English language, all studies available in full-text forms, studies related to fluid management in sepsis.

The following exclusion criteria were used: animal studies, studies published languages other than English.

Sepsis and septic shock are some of the most common medical emergencies encountered in the critical care unit. If not treated properly and on due time, sepsis can result in grave outcomes. Along with broad-spectrum antibiotics, fluid resuscitation has a fundamental role in the management of sepsis. We will confine our discussion to fluid

resuscitation only in this article. Choosing a specific type of solution for the management of patients with sepsis is still a favorite corner from a research point of view. A few choices are crystalloids (normal saline, ringer's lactate), albumin solution, hydroxyethyl starch (HES), pentastarch, and balanced salts solution [4]. Though crystalloids are the most favorite and most commonly used in the management of sepsis, evidence from randomized trials and meta-analyses reports no difference in mortality compared to albumin solution [5]. On the other hand, hydroxyethyl starch and pentastarch showed high mortality versus crystalloids [6]. Interestingly, a small study of 149 patients showed lower mortality odds with the use of balanced salts solution compared to crystalloids [7].

Despite comprehensive research, the basic fundamental question about the quantity of fluid required for the treatment of septic shock is still open for debate. One of the most used clinical approaches to adjusting the amount of fluid given in septic shock is via calculating adjusted body weight [8]. Recent guidelines suggest that patients with septic shock should receive a rapid fluid infusion of at least 30 ml/kg of crystalloids in the first three hours of presentation and then tailoring it to the hemodynamic response of the patient. Generally, patients need to have received 4.0 to 6.0 liters of fluids in the first six hours of therapy [9-11]. These guidelines seem straightforward but fluid management in a clinical setting can be challenging at times and therefore, there must be an individualized approach to each case of septic shock. Among the clinicians and intensivists, there are two different approaches to fluids resuscitation i.e liberal vs restrictive [12].

In the liberal fluid resuscitation approach, the amount of fluid administered is typically given 100-130 ml/kg to more than 160 ml/kg during the initial 72 hours of therapy and had been used as the standard of care for managing patients with sepsis and septic shock in the past, owing to the success of early goal-directed therapy in 2001 [13]. But with the emergence of harm evidence associated with aggressive fluid resuscitation raised a question mark on guidelines. The harmful effects associated with aggressive fluid therapy, firstly, are the result of direct effects on the cardiovascular system functioning, and secondly, due to deleterious effects on other organs functioning [14]. The apparent improvement in the hemodynamic parameters occurs initially during aggressive fluid therapy but cardiovascular function and mortality appear to worsen later on [15]. The pathogenesis of direct cardiotoxicity associated with large volume resuscitation is not known but can be due to myocardial edema, oxidative stress on cellular

organelles such as mitochondria, thrombi in the microvasculature, and increased permeability of the sarcolemmal membrane [16]. Studies have also suggested that large volume resuscitation induces vasodilation, and may change the hypo-dynamic state induced by septic shock into a hyperdynamic state and may result in various complications associated with it [17]. Glycocalyx degradation occurs with the administration of a large volume of fluids and can be estimated by circulating levels of hyaluronan in the blood. A recent study demonstrated that in-hospital mortality was associated with glycocalyx injury [18]. Some fluids have pro-inflammatory properties, the highest being of the hypertonic fluids, further deteriorating sepsis [19-20].

One of the major complications associated with aggressive, large volume fluid resuscitation is the development of fluid overload. Accumulation of 10 % or greater fluid in the body is termed as fluid overload. All major organ systems are affected by fluid overload, whether directly or indirectly. Fluid overload may lead to CNS dysfunction resulting in impaired cognition, cerebral edema, and diminished cerebral perfusion due to increased intracranial hypertension. It can also lead to pulmonary edema resulting in decreased lung volumes and hypoxia, and impaired cardiac contractility causing decreased cardiac output. Fluid overload may also cause decreased gut motility and venous congestion in renal and hepatic vasculature [21].

To reduce the mortality associated with fluid resuscitation, studies were conducted using an alternative approach to fluid resuscitation in the management of sepsis. Instead of large volume resuscitation, an alternative approach was to restrict the fluid volume and see how it affects the complications and outcomes in septic patients. Over the decade after early goal-directed therapy trials, further trials were conducted with a more restrictive approach to fluid administration to a septic patient and yet it did not demonstrate increased mortality or adverse outcomes [22]. Another study in 2017, showed a high mortality rate in septic patients when treated with high volume fluid therapy [23]. To date no study has been published yet, showing that a more restrictive approach to fluid resuscitation leads to poor outcomes in patients with sepsis [24]. Yet multiple studies have shown that aggressive fluid therapies are associated with multiple above-mentioned complications and increased deaths.

Vasopressors can be used to augment the effect of fluids. Dopamine and norepinephrine have been traditionally used in clinical practice [25]. They work by improving the mean arterial pressure

through vasoconstriction and increasing heart rate and cardiac contractility. Studies have proved that norepinephrine has a clearcut advantage over dopamine in improving mean arterial pressure and urine output in patients with septic shock and the use of dopamine is associated with increased mortality and arrhythmic events compared to norepinephrine [26].

CONCLUSIONS:

Previously, aggressive high-volume fluid resuscitation was the standard of care in managing patients with septic shock. However, we conclude that high volume fluid therapy is associated with risks of developing hemodynamic compromise, organ dysfunction, and increased mortality. On the other hand, a more restrictive approach to fluid administration demonstrates better outcomes and low risk of complications associated with fluid administration. Vasopressors can be used, if needed, to augment the fluid therapy. We recommend adopting a more conservative, individualized, patient-response based approach regarding fluid administration in treating patients with sepsis and septic shock.

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